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SUPPORT OF UNIVERSITY TEACHERS: TOWARDS A PROPOSED PLAN OF ACTION

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ABSTRACT

The exploration of the core competencies and organizational support among university teachers holds diverse significance, including the teaching outcomes for learners, professional advancement of teachers, efficiency in education systems, etc. This study aimed to delve into their correlation by conducting a survey and interviews on two hundred and forty-four (244) teachers from ten (10) universities in Guangxi, China, analyzing the challenges encountered in improving the two, and proposing action plans to solve these challenges.

Upon data statistics and analysis, it was concluded that the grand mean for core competencies among university teachers was 3.78. with over-all verbal description as HIGH, indicating an overwhelming consensus within the university teacher regarding their capabilities in areas such as academic competencies, teaching skills, scientific research, intercultural mindset, emotion and attitudes. The grand mean of organizational support was 3.54, with over-all verbal description as AGREE, presenting widespread agreement of university teachers regarding work support, benefit concern and value identification. In addition, data analysis manifested a positive correlation between these two variables, confirming the hypothesis proposed in this study and highlighting the significance and value of it.

In conclusion, comprehensive action plans have been proposed encompassing both individual and organizational dimensions, aiming to improve the core competencies of university teachers and organizational support, enhance the all-round abilities of teachers and promote the development of the educational sector.

Keywords: *core competencies, organizational support, university teachers*

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I. INTRODUCTION

In terms of quality education under the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), this agenda expressly clarifies that by 2030, there will be a significant increase in the number of qualified teachers. This purpose is to be achieved through international cooperation for teacher training initiatives in developing regions, especially the least developed countries and the small island developing states.

It is worth noting that China attaches great importance to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development in terms of quality education, making a proactive response. At the Fourth Session of the 12th National People's Congress held in March 2016, The thirteenth Five-Year Plan was approved, which successfully combines the Agenda for Sustainable Development with China's medium and long-term development plan. More specifically, the focus on strengthening the construction of the teaching staff is explicitly stated that: "Education is paramount, teachers are the foundation. The fundamental principle of achieving excellent results of education lies in having outstanding teachers. The qualifications of teachers should be strictly verified, and their competencies should be continuously improved in order to strive to foster a high-quality professional teaching team with noble moral, exquisite skills, reasonable structure, and extraordinary vitality."

In order to promote the implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, in September 2016, China elaborately designed and officially released the "China's National Plan on Implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development." based on its unique circumstances. It combined the 17 sustainable development goals with China's actual situation, addressed each target specifically by analyzing it separately, actively taking comprehensive approaches in various fields with responsible attitudes.

Within China's implementation plan for the 17 Sustainable Development Goals, it is specifically stated in the Sustainable Development Education Goal 4 that: by 2030, there will be a significant increase in the number of qualified teachers, including international cooperation for teacher training in developing countries, especially the least developed countries and small island developing States. It is evident that China has also put increasing the number of qualified teachers on the national agenda at the same time, indicating the profound significance to the education system in China and even the world. In a word, within the context of sustainable development and high-quality education, both from the global and

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Chinese perspectives, there exists a great emphasis on the cultivation of qualified teachers.

Universities are the fertile ground for cultivating outstanding talents, the position for spreading advanced knowledge, and the cradle for shaping perfect personality. Qualified teachers serve as the backbone of universities, emblematic of universities, and also the trailblazer in fostering societal progression and civilization advancement. They are the disseminators of knowledge, the engineers of the soul, burdened with the crucial responsibility of promoting the development and fortification of the nation. As the saying goes, "A great university is not defined by its imposing edifices, but by its illustrious professors." aiming to illuminate that a university can be called a university is not how many buildings it has, but how many masters and qualified teachers it has.

As an individualized social profession, university teachers will inevitably integrate their teaching, research, study, life and other aspects into the group organization on which they rely for survival, so they have a strong need for a sense of belonging and dependence on the working environment. The fulfillment of this need cannot be solely achieved by individual teachers, but necessitates the utmost attention and substantial support from related organizational management sectors such as schools, society, and the state. Only through the comprehensive planning and harmonious cooperation of various organizations and departments can the unique attributes of the teaching profession be fully comprehended, thereby meeting the needs of teachers. In accordance with the principle of reciprocity, once university teachers genuinely experience organizational support, it will invariably motivate them to operate with dedication and enthusiasm. This will culminate in the fruitful contribution of their efforts back to the institution, thereby achieving a mutually beneficial outcome between faculty and the organization. Hence, the exploration of university teachers' core competencies from the perspective of organizational support can significantly enhance their sense of career achievement, job satisfaction, and professional fulfillment. This fosters an enhancement in educational standards, cultivating a multitude of talents within society that exhibit robust market competitiveness.

Up to now, some experts and scholars have carried out research on the way to cultivate Chinese teachers' competencies from the perspective of organizational support, but there are few studies on the way to cultivate core competencies among Chinese university teachers from this same angle. As such, research in this area needs to be enriched. In light of this, this study will incorporate

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the variables of organizational support and core competencies of university teachers. Participants of this research is university teachers in Guangxi, China, aiming to comprehensively analyze and discuss the relationship between organizational support and teachers' core competencies in universities. It scrutinizes the challenges encountered at both the organizational level and individual level with a view to formulating strategies and recommendations on how to foster organizational support so as to advance the cultivation of teachers' core competencies in our nation's educational sector, thus promoting the rapid and steady development of higher education.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Core Competencies of University Teachers

Higher education is indicative of a nation's proficiency and potential in educational development, thereby cultivating and advancing the core competencies of university teachers as crucial elements promoting the high-quality progression of higher education. The core competencies of university teachers refer to those indispensable character and pivotal capabilities that ensure teachers can adapt to sustainable advancement and societal progression. The researcher in this part comprehensively explained the scholar's definitions of university teachers' core competencies from varied disciplines to broaden the research perspective.

Blašková et al. (2015) pointed out that the range encompassed within core competencies of teacher was extensive, which was not only limited to the competence of teaching, profession and also includes communication. But to some extent, different perspectives on the cultivation of teachers' competencies provided an overview of the internal quality or nature of these competencies in themselves. Based on this point, in the research process, scholars should not solely consider capabilities such as educational knowledge, professional training, and communication skills, but general aptitudes also ought to be taken into account.

According to Sha (2022), the term "core competencies of university counselors" was defined in terms of the essential qualities that university counselors must cultivate during their engagement with students' ideological and political education. These core competencies of university counselors referred to their stable, unique, exceptional character traits and capabilities in the process of carrying out their work. These firm character attributes and professional abilities

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could support university counselors to effectively guide student affairs, fostering higher ideological and political quality and moral cultivation among university students. In this regard, the core competencies essentially referred to enhancing university students' ideological, political and moral qualities. That is to say, it's because the peculiar characteristics of counselors which enabled them to adeptly convert theories, competencies, knowledge, etc., into the ideological and political cultivation of university students in their duties, subsequently shaping them to embody the moral attributes required by the Party and the country.

Xue and Wang (2018) expressed that it's imperative for university teachers in the realm of ideological and political education to possess core competencies that meet modern requirements, so as to align with the current training requirements for university students' core competencies, thereby genuinely implementing the fundamental task of fostering morality and cultivating talent. Specifically speaking, the core competencies for university teachers of political and ideological courses in the new era mainly included the following parts: excellent political qualities to guide students in forming the great view of world, life, and even worth, and actively cultivating and practicing socialist core values; noble moral accomplishment to shape students' correct moral cognition and value judgments; solid academic abilities to engage students in cultivating lifelong learning habits and fostering innovative practices; the social competencies of participating in social affairs and taking social responsibility leads students to learn to deal with the relationship between themselves and society, making students become people who possess tangible social responsibility and are brave enough to take up challenges.

This study analyzed it from the perspectives of academic competencies; teaching skills; scientific research; intercultural mindset; emotion and attitudes.

Organizational Support

Eisenberger et al. (1986) perceived organizational support (POS) referred to employee perceptions regarding the extent to which their employer "attached great importance to their contributions and concerned their well-being". In the social exchange between employees and employers, it was equivalent to employees' commitment to the organization, even though it was based on their perceptions rather than the organizations' perspective. In a word, this idea embodied "employees' perception concerning the organization's commitment to them". Beliefs regarding organizational commitment were thought to originate from interactions between employees with other members regarded as

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representatives of the organizations; subsequently, attributions relating to those individuals and interactions were then extended across the entirety of the organizations.

Frear et al. (2018) observed that employees who felt supported by their supervisors exhibited superior performance and demonstrated enhanced loyalty towards their employers. In order to encourage supervisor support, organizations should supply supervisors with support models, carefully communicating expectations pertaining to supervisor support. Generally speaking, support from organizations and supervisors plays a significant role in fostering positive outcomes of employees, which contribute positively to the health and growth of the entire organization. Subjectively, employees who perceive employer support demonstrated superior performance and dedicativeness compared to those lacking such perceptions. Employees receiving their supervisors support tended to exhibit similar responses.

Perceived organizational support (POS) in this study included work support; benefit concern and value identification.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research mainly used correlational research to explore the relationship between core competencies of university teachers and perceived organizational support (POS). involving survey questionnaires, literature analysis, interviews, observations etc. A correlational [research design](#) is used to investigate the dynamic relationships between the study variables, wherein researchers refrain from controlling or manipulating any of these important elements. It effectively illustrates the strength and/or direction of correlation present between two (or more) variables under various investigations.

The participants in this study randomly selected two hundred and forty-four (244) full-time teachers from ten (10) universities in Guangxi, Chian.

Upon the completion of all necessary preparations, 30 participants were specifically chosen to finish the questionnaire survey during pilot testing by means of Wenjuanxing, successfully confirming in the final results that both the credibility and effectiveness of the questionnaire had been met effectively.

To ensure the credibility and efficacy of the questionnaire, five (5) esteemed validators were solicited prior to commencement of formal research, with their task being meticulously revising and verifying the content of these questions.

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IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Correlation analysis is an important statistical method employed to evaluate the intensity of relationship between two or more variables. It primarily focuses on the correlation, association, or dependence among variables and helps to understand how they change with each other. Conventionally it utilized across various domains such as education, economics, biostatistics, and so on. This analysis enables researcher to determine the correlations among variables, thereby improving their understanding of data and making relevant decisions. Correlation analysis was used in this study to explore the relationship between core competencies of university teachers and organizational support.

Work Support and Core Competencies

The significance of gaining professional cooperation from the institution where one works is paramount in the enhancement of core competencies for university teachers. Table 1 shows the relationship between core competencies of university teachers and work support.

Table 1 Work Support and Core Competencies (N=244)

Core Competencies	Peason (r) Correlation	Significant (p value)	Findings
Academic Competencies	0.50	0.00	Average significant
Scientific Research	0.45	0.00	Average significant
Emotion and Attitudes	0.43	0.00	Average significant
Teaching Skills	0.42	0.00	Average significant
Intercultural Mindset	0.30	0.00	Weak significant
GRAND	0.50	0.00	Average significant

From table 1, it can be seen that there is an average positive correlation between work support and the improvement of university teachers' core competencies, with the grand correlation coefficient $r=0.50$, and the p -value (0.00) lower than 0.05.

As the conclusions of this survey indicated, there was a significant and positive correlation evident between work support and five dimensions of university teachers' core competencies. Specifically, these metrics encompass a general positive correlation across four dimensions: academic competencies with the correlation coefficient $r=0.50$, and the p -value (0.00) lower than 0.05; scientific research with the correlation coefficient $r=0.45$, and the p -value (0.00) lower than

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0.05; emotion and attitudes with the correlation coefficient $r = 0.43$, and the p -value (0.00) lower than 0.05; teaching skills with the correlation coefficient $r = 0.42$, and the p -value (0.00) lower than 0.05. This manifests that higher educational institutions can enhance the improvement of teachers' core competencies through diverse work-related support mechanisms. For instance, universities fully mobilize teachers' enthusiasm for work, inspire them to participate in studies and training opportunities abroad, provide timely care and assistance, as well as offer opportunities for career promotion.

As the survey findings indicate, the correlation coefficient of work support and intercultural mindset is 0.30, with a statistically significant p -value (0.00). This value falls within the interval of 0.21 to 0.40, indicating an average positive correlation between the two variables, thereby reinforcing the imperative for educational institutions to implement proactive strategies that cultivate teachers' core competencies, particularly when it comes to providing work support.

Benefit Concern and Core Competencies

The establishment of a lucid, impartial and stimulating benefit mechanism has a positive impact on fostering the underlying core competencies essential for university teachers at educational institutions. Table 2 explains an examination of organizational benefit concern in scholarly pursuits and the improvement of university teachers' core competencies within higher education settings.

Table 2 indicates that the benefit concern reveals an average positive correlation with the improvement of university teachers' core competencies, with an over-all correlation coefficient r of 0.44, and the p -value of 0.00 lower than 0.05.

As can be seen from the survey results, benefit concern exhibits an average positive correlation with academic competencies and scientific research, and their correlations coefficient r are 0.45 and 0.44 respectively, in the range of 0.41 to 0.60, both accompanied by p -value (0.00) and lower than 0.05. However, the corresponding correlations coefficient r for benefit concern are weaker at 0.36 with emotion and attitudes 0.32 with teaching skills, and 0.25 with intercultural mindset. Their respective p -values are again 0.00, indicating a weak positive correlation all resting on a range from 0.21 to 0.40.

Table 1 Benefit Concern and Core Competencies (N=244)

Core Competencies	Peason (r) Correlation	Significant (p value)	Findings
Academic Competencies	0.45	0.00	Average Significant

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Scientific Research	0.44	0.00	Average Significant
Emotion and Attitudes	0.36	0.00	Weak Significant
Teaching Skills	0.32	0.00	Weak Significant
Intercultural Mindset	0.25	0.00	Weak Significant
GRAND	0.44	0.00	Average Significant

This may indicate the following points: Firstly, universities may not be sufficiently securing access to adequate resources for the teachers in their scientific research pursuits, including funding, experimental equipment, and literature search tools. These aspects increase the difficulty of teachers engaged in scientific research activities and reduce their enthusiasm to engage. Secondly, it may also be because schools provide less opportunity for teachers to participate in cross-cultural training, seminars and research projects. Finally, teachers rarely get support and recognition from schools and leaders in their work, which reduces their emotional involvement and heightens their negative attitude. In light of these factors, universities should take active measures to continuously improve the welfare benefits of teachers and further stimulate the enhancement of their core competencies.

Value Identification and Core Competencies

The profound influence of value identification on the improvement of core competencies among university teachers denotes a substantial impact. This fosters an enhanced commitment and increased dedication in educational pursuits, further promoting professional growth and overall development within each university. Table 3 specifically explores the correlation between value identification and the elevation of core competencies within university teachers.

From the findings presented in table 3, it is apparent that average positive correlations exist between value identification and aspects of academic competencies, teaching skills, scientific research, emotion and attitude, with respective *r* correlation coefficients of 0.51, 0.42, 0.46 and 0.47, their *p*-values explicitly set at 0.00, below the conventional significance number of 0.05. Additionally, these correlation coefficients lie within the range of 0.41 to 0.60, which signify that:

Table 2 Value Identification and Core Competencies (N=244)

Core Competencies	Peason (<i>r</i>) Correlation	Significant (<i>p</i> value)	Findings
Academic Competencies	0.51	0.00	Average Significant

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Emotion and Attitudes	0.47	0.00	Average Significant
Scientific Research	0.46	0.00	Average Significant
Teaching Skills	0.42	0.00	Average Significant
Intercultural Mindset	0.29	0.00	Weak Significant
GRAND	0.51	0.00	Average Significant

From the above data, it can be seen that: first and foremost, many university teachers experience a high degree of value recognition, which positively influences their goal setting for instruction, making them more likely to set clear goals focused on cultivating students' disciplinary competencies through educational practices. Secondly, when teachers perceive organizational endorsement for their value identification, they may be more willing to adopt interactive and practical teaching methods to designed to engage student participation and practical application resulting in improved educational outcomes. Thirdly, teachers' feelings of value identification play a considerable role in shaping their chosen research interests and areas of focus, potentially directing them towards research directions potentially related to their value identification in order to promote the progress in that area. Fourthly, in terms of emotion and attitude, an organization's affirmation of the noble mission of education could enhance an improved level of commitment, task orientation among teachers.

Upon analysis of the collected data, it is evident that intercultural mindset bears the lowest r correlation coefficient within these dimensions at 0.29, with p -values of 0.00 that are significantly lower than 0.05, indicating a weakly positive correlation. This implies that the degree of organizational value identification by university teachers affects their adaptability in the new cultural environment, and these unaccepted and unrecognized values of the new culture may lead to their adaptation difficulties and cultural conflicts. Therefore, schools should pay attention to this aspect and take various active measures to broaden the intercultural mindset of university teachers.

Summary of the Relationship between Core Competencies and Organizational Support

Table 4 shows the summary of correlations between core competencies and organizational support.

The survey findings from table 4 indicate that organizational support, on the whole, shows average positive correlations with the improvement of university

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teachers' core competencies. The overall correlation coefficient is 0.51, and the p-value stands at 0.00, less than 0.05, emphasizing the significance of this study.

Table 3 Summary Table of Correlations with Teachers' Core Competencies (N=244)

Organizational Support	Peason (r) Correlation	Significant (p value)	Findings
Value Identification	0.51	0.00	Average Significant
Work Support	0.50	0.00	Average Significant
Benefit Concern	0.44	0.00	Average Significant
GRAND MEAN	0.51	0.00	Average Significant

According to the data above, the correlation coefficient for value identification presents as the highest one with 0.51, and its corresponding p-value is 0.00, below 0.05, suggesting a robust influence within these dimensions and prompts potential recommendations for future research studying the correlations between university teachers' core competencies and value identification in these areas. Work support holds an intermediate level ranking, the correlation coefficient is 0.50 with p-value 0.00, yet remains less than 0.05, underlining the crucial role it plays in the advancement of university teachers' competencies. Organizations ought to be mindful not to underestimate work support's pivotal role throughout this process. Benefit concern ranks lowest, showing a correlation coefficient of 0.44, which falls short of the 0.50 threshold, indicating relevance even though slightly lower compared to other dimensions, with a p-value of 0.00 also falling below 0.05, reinforcing the importance of researching this issue, advocating greater attention towards benefits for teachers, and taking additional positive measures to bolster teachers' career happiness as well as their sense of achievement.

Proposed Plan of Action for Enhancing Core Competencies among Teachers

With the rapid development of today's society, the enhancement of the core competencies of university teachers faces numerous challenges. In order to meet the needs of the times, such policies, technologies and teaching methods in the field of education will continue to develop and change, which may lead to the need for teachers to constantly adapt to new education policies and update teaching concepts and methods. This can be particularly challenging during the improvement process of their essential skills. In addition, due to the varieties in the allocation of educational resources between different regions and schools, some schools may face many problems such as insufficient teachers and outdated equipment, which will constitute a very big obstacle to the improvement of

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teachers' core competencies. Furthermore, university students come from a diverse range of backgrounds and have different learning styles and needs. Therefore, teachers need to have distinct teaching capacities for different levels and groups to meet their needs. These collectively present a great challenge to university teachers' core competencies enhancement. For this reason, the researcher proposed the following action plan:

First and foremost, the researcher would like to draw attention to the academic competencies aspect among university teachers. regarding the inadequate solid professional knowledge of teachers, it is of utmost importance that teachers adopt a series of methods and strategies to perpetually fortify their expertise. For instance, they may actively participate in specially designed professional development courses to update and improve their teaching abilities. These courses are often offered by academic institutions or professional organizations. Undeniably, perusing the latest educational research, academic articles, and pedagogical resources is an efficacious method for strengthening professional knowledge. Teachers could subscribe to subject-related journals, engage active participation in online forums to maintain awareness of discipline developments. In addition, it is necessary to encourage them to boldly join specialized communities or associations related to their field, exchange experiences with colleagues, participate in discussions, stay abreast of latest professional innovations and trends. Particularly instructive is self-assessment conducted regularly on individual teaching practices, identifying any deficiency persisting in professional knowledge, and formulating strategies and plans for improvement.

In addition, it is incumbent upon teachers to exhibit proactive learning and sustained effort by integrating various learning ways to curriculum development. This can be achieved via a series of educational resources like books, online courses, education platforms, etc., to gradually build systematic theoretical and practical knowledge of the subject through independent exploring of knowledge in related fields. Further, participants may consider attending professional training programs to improve their understanding of specific subject fields. This could take place in the form of face-to-face seminars or virtual academic courses. Lastly, if financial and other circumstances permit, personal mentorship from industry professionals may prove beneficial for comprehensive guidance and suggestions. In addition, developing a clear learning plan, including objective settings, timing

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arrangements, evaluation methods, etc., to ensure that learning is systematic and effective.

In the face of the deficiency of teachers' teaching abilities, the key lies in the continuous self-reflection and continuous learning of teachers themselves, and gradually improve and elevate their teaching capabilities. On one hand, teachers are encouraged to regularly reflect on their teaching methods to identify potential areas for improvement. They should adapt educational techniques, experiment with fresh teaching strategies, and consistently refine their teaching practices. On the other hand, setting specific, measurable teaching goals and defining the advancement anticipated over a short-term and long-term period can significantly make the promotion more targeted. Of course, it is also necessary to often observe the classes of experienced teachers and learn their teaching skills and management methods. Drawing inspiration from such encounters to adopt suitable teaching tactics that resonate best with one's unique approach. In addition, engaging in comprehensive self-assessment of one's teaching is essential, dissection of one's strengths and shortcomings must take place. Identifying areas needing enhancement could include aspects like classroom management, teaching methodology, subject knowledge and so on.

To augment their scientific research abilities, teachers should immerse themselves in subject matter comprehension deepening, broaden their advanced studies and related literature understanding, and keep pace with discipline development trends. Moreover, acquiring research methods applicable to their respective fields becomes paramount. This includes skills in empirical research, literature review, experimental design, and statistical analysis, etc. It is worth mentioning that in order to improve the efficiency and accuracy of research, teachers should learn to skillfully use various scientific research tools in the daily teaching process, including literature retrieval tools and data analysis software.

Universities can take a range of measures to help teachers consolidate their professional knowledge. This serves as an indispensable support and incentive that ensures teachers can maintain their professional standards in the field of education. Firstly, schools can regularly organize professional development activities, including seminars, training courses, lectures and research projects, so that teachers can acquire the updated teaching strategies, subject knowledge and educational technologies. Secondly, establishment of a mentoring program is advantageous where experienced teachers serve as mentors for novice educators, sharing their experiences and proficiency. Mentors can provide

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personalized guidance to help new teachers better adapt to the university environment and professional development. Thirdly, finance support for professional development could be made available by universities, which helps fund their attendance at seminars, training courses, and academic activities, thus promoting their active participate in continuous learning about the subjects.

Universitas can also take a series of measures to help teachers overcome the challenge of insufficient systematic knowledge in order to improve their professional level: Firstly, universitas can organize regular professional training, invite well-respected professionals or internal and external experts to systematically impart knowledge, and help teachers deepen their understanding of specific domains. Secondly, furnishing sufficient teaching resources such as libraries, digital libraries, and online learning platforms to aid teachers in acquiring, assimilating, and disseminating related areas' knowledge more efficaciously. Thirdly, universitas should encourage and motivate teachers to pursue lifelong learning and provide relevant reward mechanisms to stimulate their pursuit of systematic knowledge.

In addressing findings of deficiency teaching level, universities can implement a series of strategies to improve and fortify the professional development of teachers. Firstly, systematic teaching evaluation should be carried out to provide timely and specific feedback to teachers. This can be achieved through peer review, student evaluation, teaching observation, etc. Secondly, it's pivotal to organize regular teacher training, including educational theory, curriculum design, instructional methods and other aspects. These enlightening sessions can be provided either internally or externally by professional entities. Thirdly, it would be advantageous to work with each teacher to develop an individualized professional development plan that identifies development goals, timelines, and support resources. This helps teachers to enhance their teaching level more pertinently.

It should not be ignored that universities should also implement proactive measures to create a conducive academic atmosphere to research development by providing advantageous academic resources and support to enhance the research effectiveness of the whole institution: Firstly, the university stimulates teachers to organically combine research with teaching, adopt problem-driven teaching methods, and foster students' ability to proactively ask questions and solve problems. Secondly, universities can establish dedicated scientific research funds to encourage teachers to actively and boldly apply for scientific research projects, and vigorously provide financial and resource support. Thirdly, it is very

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important to actively support teachers to participate in the writing and publication of academic papers, especially those commendable works, promoting the university's reputation within academia.

V. CONCLUSION

The findings of over-all correlation coefficient r between university teachers' core competencies and organizational support represents an average positive correlation between each other, including dimensions of work support and core competencies, benefit concern and core competencies, value identification and core competencies.

Through careful examination and evaluation, it is evident that a significant correlation exists between the core competencies of university teachers and their organizational support, which indicates the significance and value of this research.

Firstly, fostering individual development for teachers can be facilitated by comprehending and developing their core competencies. By understanding and improving these competencies, teachers may better recognize their teaching styles, professional interests, and development needs. Additionally, the studies regarding organizational support can reveal how organizations deliver training activities, provide career development opportunities, and offer feedback, thus augmenting teacher satisfaction and engagement to their work.

Secondly, enriching educational quality. Exploration into the core competencies of teachers aids in clarifying the essential skills and knowledge base required by teachers, thereby promoting them to discharge their teaching roles effectively. With strong core competencies, teachers can better cultivate and apply educational theories, methods and technologies, so as to improve curriculum design and teaching results.

Thirdly, boosting organizational productivity. Research on organizational support can clarify how an institution's consideration and support for its faculty interrelate with the organization's overall performance and success. By increasing teacher satisfaction and engagement, organizations are better able to retain outstanding educational talent and improve the overall quality of education.

It is also inevitable for university teachers to encounter challenges in core competencies and organizational support, and various positive action plans should be taken to address those challenges.

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